

SROC III

Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

**November, 2-3rd 2024,
Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula, Vrdnik**

The relationship between serum cytokine levels and the development of radiation toxicity in patients with prostate cancer

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13987418

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Radiotherapy plays a significant role in the multidisciplinary approach to treating prostate cancer patients. However, some patients may develop severe adverse effects after receiving radiotherapy. Radiotoxicity may manifest in the lower gastrointestinal (GI) tract or genitourinary (GU) tract. The probability of complications in normal tissue increases as the delivered radiation dose is increased. However, there are patients with satisfactory dosimetric parameters who develop radiation toxicity and vice versa.

Prediction models that take into account additional parameters to identify patients most susceptible for developing toxicity may serve as essential factor toward a personalized radiotherapy.

Changes in the cytokines levels, such as IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-6, TGF- β 1, IFN- γ etc could also be connected with the occurrence of acute gastrointestinal and genitourinary toxicity.

A prospective cohort study of prostate cancer patients treated with radiotherapy, was performed at the Institute for oncology and radiology of Serbia from January 2016 to February 2020. Levels of cytokine concentration in serum of patients before treatment, several times during treatment and one month after radiotherapy was determined. The primary aim of this investigation is elucidation of association between the change in cytokine serum levels and development of acute radiation toxicity. Serum cytokine levels are determined with Elisa test, while acute radiation toxicity is graded using RTOG/EORTC scale.

It can be concluded that the radiation therapy, the development of an inflammatory process, and the occurrence of radiation toxicity are all related. However, further research with the aim of development of an individualized approach to radiotherapy is required.

Keywords: Prostate cancer, inflammatory biomarkers, cytokines, radiation toxicity

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2024**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

CIP – Каталогизacija у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (3 ; 2024 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Third Serbian Radiation Oncology
Congress, SROC III, November, 2nd-3rd 2024, Ethno Complex
Vrdnicka Kula, Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. – Novi
Sad : Institut za onkologiju Vojvodine, 2024 (Novi Sad : NS
digiprint). – 60 str. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200. – Str. 3: Introduction / Olivera Ivanov.

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 155485193